

1 Behavioural Adaptation to Prototype Level 3 Automated 2 Driving Systems on Public Roads

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14 **Abstract:** Behavioural adaptation refers to changes in user behaviour following the introduction to
15 changes in the road-vehicle-user system. The introduction of automated driving systems (ADS)
16 triggers changes in drivers' perception, cognition, attitudes, performance, and the driver state as
17 shown in a previous driving simulator study on repeated usage of an ADS (Metz et al., 2021). The
18 present study aims at overcoming limitations due to the driving simulator setup and replicates the
19 study design on German public roads using prototype level 3 ADS. Three different versions of a level
20 3 ADS with different operational design domains (ODD) are compared in a between group design.
21 N = 75 drivers experienced a level 3 ADS during four experimental driving sessions. The drivers were
22 free to activate / deactivate the function as they liked and to spend driving time on self-chosen side
23 tasks. With growing experience, the mental model of the system improves towards more realistic
24 expectations towards system capabilities. At the same time, acceptance and perceived safety increase
25 while stress decreases. Objective indicators of system handling are impacted by the ODD, however
26 there are no changes with repeated usage. The results from the on-road study are compared with the
27 results from the driving simulator and they are discussed with regard to the theory of behavioural
28 adaptation.

29 **Keywords:** behavioural adaptation; system usage; acceptance; attention; secondary task; reaction to
30 requests to intervene; level 3 automated driving; mental model;
31

32 **Highlights:**

- 33 • Behavioural adaptation to level 3 automated driving is studied on public roads.
- 34 • With experience, system understanding improves and expectations get more realistic.
- 35 • With experience, drivers get more relaxed and evaluate the ADS more positively.
- 36 • Driving environment and system design impact system handling.
- 37 • Results are directly compared to results from a previous simulator study
38

39 1. Introduction

40 Recently, the first vehicles equipped with level 3 automated driving functions have entered the
41 market. By definition, in level 3 automation (L3, conditional automation) all aspects of the
42 driving task are executed by the automated driving system (ADS) as long as the ADS operates
43 within its operational design domain (ODD, SAE, 2021). As soon as the ADS reaches a
44 situation outside the ODD, the ADS issues a request-to intervene (RtI) and requests the driver
45 to take control back and to continue driving manually. From the driver's perspective, L3 is the
46 first level of automation where vehicle automation can be experienced as completely self-
47 driving within system boundaries. However, as L3-ADS are mostly still in development, there
48 is limited on-road experience to understand how these systems will be used in real traffic and
49 how they will impact driver and driving behavior.

50 User studies on advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) and ADS typically focus on
51 specific aspects of user experience and behavior such as the evaluation of a specific user
52 interface (Ayoub, Zhou, Bao, & Yang, 2019; Wörle et al., 2020) or the effects of the system on
53 the driver state (Ahlström, Wörle, Ljung Aust, & Diederichs, 2023) and a particular research
54 focus has been on user behavior in transitions of control (Zhang, De Winter, Varotto, Happee,
55 & Martens, 2019). In these experiments, users typically experience ADS for the first time and
56 for a rather short time. However, it is to be expected that drivers experienced in the usage of an
57 ADS will use the system differently than they do during first contact. After experiencing the
58 behavior of an ADS in various situations and over a longer period of time, drivers will adopt
59 their behavior to a certain extent. Some of these changed behaviors might be anticipated by the
60 system designers and they are targeted by user studies as discussed above. However, users also
61 adapt their behavior in ways that are not anticipated by the designers of new systems. In this
62 context, "behavioral adaptation" (BA) is defined as "behaviours which may occur following
63 the introduction of changes to the road-vehicle-user system and which were not intended by the
64 initiators of the change" (OECD, 1990).

65 In a previous study (Metz et al., 2021), BA to L3-ADS was investigated in a driving simulator.
66 In that study, drivers used a L3-ADS for motorways during six drives taking place on six
67 different days. They were free to activate and deactivate the ADS and engage in non-driving
68 related activities (NDRAs) of their choice. The study analyzed changes in system evaluation,
69 system handling, and driving performance during request-to-intervene (RtI) situations with
70 repeated use. Results indicated BA in both the evaluation and usage of the ADS, demonstrating,
71 for example, increased acceptance and trust over time. With growing experience, drivers
72 reported higher acceptance and willingness to use the system, reduced workload, increased
73 trust, and spent less time looking at the road while engaging more in NDRAs when the ADS
74 was active. Interviews with a subsample of the study revealed that, after repeated use and
75 increased trust, drivers were more likely to use the ADS in unintended ways, such as taking a
76 nap during automated driving (Wörle & Metz, 2023). The study also found potential changes
77 in overall travel behavior with half of the sample indicating to make longer trips if they had an
78 ADS available. Therefore, the amount of travel might increase due to ADS (Lehtonen et al.,
79 2021). However, since the study was conducted in a simulated setting, some behaviors and

80 experiences might not accurately reflect real-world user behavior. For instance, participants in
81 the driving simulator study might have felt safer knowing there was no actual risk, potentially
82 influencing their behavior. Therefore, the primary goal of the study presented in this paper is to
83 investigate BA similarly to the simulator study, but in a real-world setting with drivers using a
84 prototype L3-ADS on public roads.

85 Drivers may react to reduced safety risks, such as those introduced by new safety-promoting
86 vehicle technologies, by adopting riskier driving behaviors, like increasing their travel speed
87 (Peltzman, 1975). The first theory explaining this behavioral adaptation was the Theory of Risk
88 Homeostasis (Wilde, 1982). The theory assumes that individuals have a target level of accepted
89 risk in driving situations and that they adjust their behavior such that the perceived level of risk
90 matches their target level of risk. With regard to the introduction of ADAS, it was found that
91 when using adaptive cruise control (ACC), drivers reacted more slowly to a hazardous situation
92 and they had a greater deviation from lane position than when driving without ACC (Rudin-
93 Brown & Parker, 2004). Another study found drivers to drive at higher speeds and lower
94 distances to front vehicles as well as higher engagement in a secondary task when they were
95 using a congestion tail warning system (Naujoks & Totzke, 2014).

96 The Qualitative model of Behavioral Adaptation (Rudin-Brown & Parker, 2004) specifically
97 addresses behavioral changes to ADAS and it might be applicable for the usage of ADS as well.
98 The model states that the driver's behavior depends on their internal mental model of the driving
99 task. This mental model is directly influenced by psychological variables such as the
100 individual's locus of control as well as their trust in the system. As evidenced by a number of
101 studies, trust is one of the main factors modulating driver behavior when using ADSs (Dikmen,
102 & Burns, 2017; Gold, Körber, Hohenberger, Lechner & Bengler, 2015). Trust depends amongst
103 others on the degree of experience with automation and is expected to change over time (Muir,
104 1987). Although relevant for understanding partly surprising and unwanted effects of ADAS
105 on driving safety, the analysis of BA for ADAS / ADS is not necessarily limited to unintended
106 changes. Various components of drivers' usage and evaluation of ADS can change with
107 prolonged experience of a system and therefore be impacted by BA.

108 Martens & Jenssen (2021) propose the following potential changes:

- 109 • Perceptive changes (seeing, hearing, feeling)
- 110 • Cognitive changes (comprehending, interpreting, prioritizing, selecting, deciding)
- 111 • Performance changes (driving, system handling, error)
- 112 • Driver state changes (attentiveness/awareness, workload, stress, drowsiness)
- 113 • Attitudinal changes (acceptance, rejection, overreliance, mistrust)
- 114 • Changes in the adaptation to environmental conditions (weather, visibility, etc.)

115 By definition, the term 'behavioral adaptation' relates to time because it implies that changes
116 in behavior are a result of being exposed to e.g., a certain ADAS / ADS and experiencing it
117 over time in different situations (Patten, 2013). There are theories that distinguish different
118 phases in this timely development of BA (Martens & Jenssen, 2012; Saad, Hjalmdahl, Cañas,
119 Alonso, Garayo, Macchi et al., 2004). According to Saad et al. (2004), drivers experience the
120 system in different situations and different environments. Through this, they understand the
121 system's functionality as well as system limits and build an appropriate level of trust. In the

122 theory, two phases in the learning process are differentiated: the “learning phase” in which the
123 driver learns how to operate the system, identifies system limits and internalizes the system
124 functionality, and the “integration phase” in which the driver integrates the system into the
125 management of the overall driving task. Martens & Jenssen (2012) go beyond those two phases:
126 They define a first encounter (first day, 1–6 hours), a learning phase (3–4 weeks, respectively
127 10-40 h), a trust phase (1–6 months), an adjustment phase (6–12 months) and a readjustment
128 phase (1–2 years).

129 The approach of considering the process of BA as different phases seems to be a good start for
130 the investigation of BA. However, as long as there is a limited number of vehicles with L3-
131 ADS on the market and on the roads, it is difficult to go beyond the learning or trust phase with
132 the available prototype systems. For the investigation of ADAS, a few hours to a few weeks are
133 considered to be short-term usage whereas long-term usage is meant to last at least 6 months
134 (Patten, 2013). Nonetheless, studies looking at BA in the early stage of the timely changes
135 occurring during the first drives with a L3-ADS will bring valuable insight that goes beyond
136 what is known from short experiments on L3-ADS. A study like the one by Metz et al. (2021)
137 goes beyond the frequently chosen approach of investigating changes over repeated trials within
138 one experimental session (e.g., Forster, Hergeth, Naujoks, Beggiato et al. 2019; Louw,
139 Goncalves, Torrao et al., 2020) but is clearly not sufficient to study the full process of BA like
140 it could be done in a field-operational test for systems already available on the market. Due to
141 practical limitations, it is not possible to study the full process of BA where changes are still
142 expected to occur even after several months of usage. Instead, in the presented work the focus
143 is on the beginning of this process including the first encounter, the learning phase and maybe
144 the beginning of the trust phase. It is expected that during the learning phase there is still some
145 change of behavior. For the trust phase a more constant level is expected.

146 2. Objectives

147 As previously described, a driving simulator study on BA to L3-ADS was conducted, focusing
148 on the early phases of BA. Building on this, a similar on-road study is now being conducted
149 where drivers can use L3-ADS on public roads. The aim is to investigate to what extent the
150 increase in acceptance and trust observed in the simulator setting can be replicated in a real-
151 world setting. In the current study, as in the simulator study, a variety of independent parameters
152 are investigated to provide a comprehensive understanding of BA in the context of L3-ADS.
153 The study addresses several types of behavior for which BA might occur (Martens & Jenssen,
154 2021) in a rather explorative approach: perceptive changes, cognitive changes, performance
155 changes, driver state changes and attitudinal changes.

156 3. Materials and Methods

157 3.1. Experimental design

158 An on-road study using prototype SAE level 3 ADS was conducted. The study included data
159 collection in three ODDs. ODD 1 was an urban motorway with a maximum speed of 60 km/h
160 and ODD 2 and 3 were on a motorway with a maximum speed of 130 km/h. In ODD 1 and 2,

161 the system was not able to change the lane in automated mode, in ODD 3 it could. ODD 1 will
 162 be referred to as “Urban”, ODD 2 as “Motorway-LC” and ODD 3 as “Motorway+LC” in this
 163 paper. A mixed design was chosen. The factor ODD was varied as a between-subjects factor
 164 with the three levels of Urban vs. Motorway-LC vs. Motorway+LC. The factor Drive Number
 165 was varied as a within-subjects factor with the levels drive number 1 to drive number 4.

166 3.2. Data collection and experimental procedure

167 *For organizational reasons, the data collection took place in three waves.*

168 Table 1 gives an overview over the data collection and the ODDs. Participants were recruited
 169 separately for each ODD, primarily from the Munich region. Due to organizational reasons,
 170 about half of the sample consisted of BMW employees not involved in AD development, the
 171 other half were ordinary drivers not linked to BMW. All participants were invited and scheduled
 172 for four drives on four different days.

173 After scheduling the dates for the experimental drives, all participants received written
 174 information and a link to the pre-questionnaire via mail before the first session. In the
 175 introductory session, participants were informed about the schedule for their test drives and
 176 signed an informed consent form as well as a data privacy agreement. Before each session, they
 177 were told the length of the oncoming trip and they were free to prepare for the drive as they
 178 wished. They filled in the pre-drive questionnaire and the mental model questionnaire before
 179 their first drive and were then introduced to the vehicle with the ADS. Then, they experienced
 180 the first drive which took about one hour. Participants were instructed to use the ADS as they
 181 would use it if they had it available in their personal car. During the drive, vehicle data, eye-
 182 tracking data and videos of the driving scene and the driver were recorded. After the drive,
 183 participants filled in the post-drive questionnaire. In the second, third and fourth drive,
 184 participants experienced the drive with the ADS on the same route and filled in the post-drive
 185 questionnaire again. After the fourth driving session, the external participants were
 186 compensated for their participation. Due to the real-world systems still being at a prototype
 187 stage, current safety regulations in Europe do not allow unsupervised testing of L3-ADS with
 188 ordinary drivers on public roads (Lee & Hess, 2020). Therefore, throughout all drives, a safety
 189 driver was present on the front passenger seat.
 190

191 *Table 1: Overview over data collection and experimental setup for the three ODDs.*

	ODD		
	Urban	Motorway-LC	Motorway+LC
Data collection	Sept + Nov 2022	May - Aug 2023	Jul – Sept 2023
Drive No	Repeated use - 4 drives per participant		
Chosen road	Urban Motorway (Mittlerer Ring, Munich)	Motorway (A92 north of Munich)	Motorway (A92 north of Munich)

AD	Urban ODD, vmax = 60km/h,	Motorway ODD, vmax = 130km/h
Lane changes	no automated lane change	automated lane change

192

193 3.3. Description of AD functionalities

194 The utilized system was a SAE level 3 ADS implemented in a prototype vehicle. For the
 195 experiment, a prototype BMW X5 was used which was equipped with the ADS, with a data
 196 logging system and extra pedals and controls for the safety driver. The ADS incorporated
 197 longitudinal and lateral control, operating up to 130 km/h on motorways and up to 60 km/h on
 198 urban motorways. The ODD for both road types was specified as motorways with separated
 199 carriageways, from entering the motorway at the entrance line to reaching the exit lane. To
 200 enable non-professional participants to experience L3-ADS as drivers on public roads, a
 201 specially trained safety driver in the co-driver seat was a crucial part of the safety concept.
 202 While driving in level 3, the safety-driver's task was to supervise the surrounding traffic and to
 203 intervene if necessary. For this purpose, driving school pedals and a status monitoring system
 204 for the safety-driver were installed. This safety concept allows drivers to divert their attention
 205 from the driving task and engage in NDRAs. The availability of fully automated lane changes
 206 was varied in this study: In the Urban and Motorway-LC conditions, all lane changes had to be
 207 initiated by the driver. The driver had to take back vehicle control and could either conduct a
 208 manual lane change or initiate a level 2 automated lane change function by holding the turn
 209 lever. The level 3 function had to be reactivated after the lane change. In the Motorway-LC
 210 condition, fully automated lane changes were included in the ADS, the driver did not have to
 211 initiate any lane change and experienced level 3 driving seamlessly throughout the entire ODD.
 212 When reaching the end of the ODD (e.g. the exit) a planned RtI was issued. Drivers had
 213 sufficient time to end potential NDRAs and to take control back. This could be done by either
 214 putting both hands on the steering wheel or braking or pressing again the button used for the
 215 activation of ADS.

216 3.4. Data logging and questionnaires

217 During all drives, there was a continuous logging of vehicle data from CAN-bus such as speed,
 218 steering wheel angle, pedal positions, distance to surrounding objects etc. The logging included
 219 information from the driver monitoring system which assess where the driver looks at as well
 220 as a synchronized logging of video. The video consisted of a view of the driver as well as of
 221 the road to the front and to the back.

222 All participants completed three types of questionnaires: The pre-drive questionnaire, the
 223 mental model questionnaire, and the post-drive questionnaire. All questionnaires were
 224 implemented in LimeSurvey and were filled in during the sessions using a tablet. The pre-drive
 225 questionnaire was sent via an online link and completed before the first drive. The mental model
 226 questionnaire was filled in upon arrival at the test premises before the first test drive and
 227 together with the post-drive questionnaire after each test drive.

- The pre-drive questionnaire included questions on the participants' demographics, mobility habits, experience with automation and personality scales like the Brief Sensation Seeking Scale (BSSS; Hoyle, Stephenson, Palmgreen, Lorch, & Donohew, 2002), the Big Five Inventory (BFI-10; Rammstedt, Kemper, Klein, Beierlein, & Kovalena, 2014) and four items from the Technology Readiness Index (TRI; Parasuraman, 2000).
- The mental model questionnaire included 23 statements on the ADS, for example on its operational design domain or its general features. Participants had to state whether the statement is correct or incorrect and how confident they are about their decision (Metz, Wörle, & Neukum, 2024). The questionnaire consists mainly of two parts: items describing characteristics of L3-ADS than can be right or wrong and items describing situations that could potentially be in or out the ODD.
- The post-drive questionnaire included questions on the experience of the drive such as the Acceptance Scale (Van Der Laan, Heino, & De Waard, 1997), custom items on trust, perceived safety and mobility, non-driving related activities and a scale on the perceived criticality of situations encountered during the drive. The specifically developed questionnaire items mostly consisted of statements which the participants can agree or disagree with on a 5-point scale. There were additional items addressing mode awareness and the split of responsibilities between ADS and driver using a 7-point Likert-scale. Furthermore, willingness to pay was assessed with a categorical item giving 5 categories between 0€ and >7000€ and the occurrence of motion sickness with a y/n question.

3.5. Study sample

Table 2 shows the description of the overall sample grouped by ODD condition. A total of N = 98 participants was scheduled for the study while N = 75 completed all four driving sessions. Besides information on the drivers, the table gives an overview of relevant aspects of the drives (e.g. duration of driving with the ADS active, number of lane changes in ODD etc.)

Table 2: Description of study sample. The table shows means, the value in brackets is the standard deviation.

	Urban	Motorway-LC	Motorway+LC
N (first drive)	31	35	32
N (four drives)	25	28	22
Mean age	36.1 (13.1)	31.5 (10.8)	32.7 (11.9)
Gender: Female/Male/Div	15/16/0	14/21/0	13/18/1
Mean Sensation Seeking total score	27.7 (4.5)	28.1 (4.7)	27.8 (5.0)
Mean Technology Readiness Index	3.4 (1.0)	3.8 (0.9)	3.5 (1.1)
Mean duration AD available (min)	30.3	36.8	37.3
Mean duration AD active (min)	25.9	22.8	33.3
Mean N (Lane Changes in ODD)	3.5	26.6	42.0
Mean N planned takeover requests	2.9	1.1	1.4

259 3.6. Data Analysis

260 A variety of indicators was analyzed to assess BA for the different behavioral categories (see
261 Table 3). The subjective evaluation of the ADS after each drive was assessed for the van der
262 Laan acceptance scale (subscales usefulness and satisfying) and the dimensions willingness to
263 use, perceived safety, trust & perceived reliability, fun / pleasure to drive, workload / stress and
264 attention while driving each measured with specific questionnaire items. For the mental model
265 questionnaire, the following indicators were calculated: percentage correct answers for the
266 mental model items (part 1) as well as percentage of situations believed to be inside ODD (part
267 2).

268 The continuously logged objective data was used to analyze handling and usage of the ADS by
269 the drivers and to investigate drivers' performance at RtIs. The following indicators were
270 analyzed:

- 271 • System usage: proportion of time the ADS was activated [%] in relation to the time it
272 was available and number of lane changes while being in ODD. This was derived from
273 signals logged in the vehicle.
- 274 • NDRA involvement: proportion of time with active ADS that drivers spent on NDRAs
275 like interaction with their smartphone, interaction with the passenger (i.e. the safety
276 driver), interaction with the infotainment system and other NDRAs [%]. All indicators
277 related to NDRAs were derived from continuous coding of the video.
- 278 • Distribution of attention: Percent eyes on road, EoR [%], derived from the driver
279 monitoring system installed in the vehicle. A gaze was coded as being on the road
280 whenever the eye tracking system detected that gaze was in the direction of the
281 windscreen.

282 To evaluate driver's reaction to RtIs, two approaches were chosen:

- 283 • Reaction times were calculated that are defined as the duration between the start of the
284 RtI and the first time point the analyzed driver reaction was observed (hands on the
285 steering wheel, deactivation of the ADS, see e.g. Wiedemann, Naujoks, Wörle,
286 Kenntner-Mabiala, Kaussner, & Neukum, 2018).
- 287 • Expert rating of takeover performance based on the video. Therefore, the Take-Over
288 Controllability (TOC) rating was performed (Naujoks, Wiedemann, Schömig, Jarosch,
289 & Gold (2018), for more details see <https://toc-rating.de/en/>) which defines a
290 standardized procedure for the evaluation of take-over situations. Relevant dimensions
291 for evaluation are provided with defined criteria for the different rating categories. In
292 the end, a final rating is given on a 10-point scale. Values <4 reflect takeover
293 situations without errors, values between 4 and 6 situations with errors but without
294 endangerment and values > 6 situations with a danger either to the own vehicle or to
295 other traffic participants.

296 The factors Drive No (drive 1 to drive 4) as well as ODD (Urban, Motorway-LC,
297 Motorway+LC) were used as predictors. For statistical testing, the effects of Drive No and ODD
298 were tested with a mixed model ANOVA (Drive No as a within-subject and ODD as a between-
299 subject factor). In the results section, graphs show means and 95%-confidence intervals.

300 Last, the correlations between the different measures were analyzed to explore to which extent
301 the different types of changes are interrelated. For this, linear correlations were calculated

302 separately for the first and fourth drive but always taking all ODDs together. As results showed
 303 a strong impact of the characteristics of the ODD on objective indicators like percentage of
 304 system activation, these indicators were z-standardized per ODD before calculating the
 305 correlations. This was done for percentage of system activation, percent eyes on road time and
 306 percentage of time spent on interaction with the personal smartphone.

307
 308 *Table 3: Categories of behavioral changes and indicators used in the analysis.*

Type of change	Indicator
Perceptive changes	Percent eyes on road Questionnaire items on attention while driving with ADS
Attitudinal changes	Questionnaire items on willingness to use, acceptance, trust, perceived safety & reliability
Cognitive changes	Results from mental model questionnaire NDRA involvement Questionnaire items on NDRA involvement
Driver state changes	Questionnaire items on workload, stress, motion sickness
Performance changes	Indicators of system handling Reaction times to RtIs Takeover performance at RtIs (TOC-rating)

309 4. Results

310 4.1. Acceptance and evaluation

311 As can be seen in Figure 1, participants evaluated the ADS overall positively. For instance, they
 312 stated that driving with the ADS was fun and not stressful and that they would like to use the
 313 system if it was in their cars. With repeated usage, there was a significant change of evaluation
 314 for items measuring willingness to use, perceived safety, for experienced stress and intention
 315 to attend to NDRAs. With increasing experience with the ADS, drivers stated that they would
 316 like to use it more, that they felt safer, that they experienced ADS behavior as less risky and
 317 more appropriate. Consequently, stress while driving with ADS decreased and willingness to
 318 attend to NDRAs increased (see Table 4).

319 The three different ODDs differed mainly with regard to the experienced safety while driving.
 320 In the urban ODD, the ADS was subjectively less safe, there were more risky situations and
 321 consequently drivers experienced the ADS as less reliable and trusted it less. The three ODDs
 322 did not differ in other aspects like willingness to use or experienced fun or workload.

323 Based on the items addressing mode awareness and split of responsibilities, drivers agreed with
 324 increasing experience more with the statement that they knew how responsibilities were split
 325 between the ADS and the driver ($F(3,159)=4.5, p<.01$) and when they needed to be attentive
 326 ($F(2,333)=2.7, p<.05$). For the van der Laan scale, there was neither an impact of Drive number
 327 on the experienced satisfaction nor on usefulness. However, on both scales the ADS was rated

328 less positively for the urban ODD compared to the two other ODDs (Satisfaction $F(2,72)=4.2$,
 329 $p<.05$, Usefulness $F(2,72)=7.7$, $p<.001$).

330 Drive No: 1 2 3 4
 331 Figure 1: Effect of condition on drivers' agreement with questionnaire items. * marks statements with
 332 a significant main effect of drive number. The items are grouped based on the concepts: willingness to
 333 use, perceived safety, trust & perceived reliability, fun / pleasure to drive, workload / stress and
 334 attention while driving.

335 Table 4: Results of ANOVAs testing for the effects of Drive number and ODD on the questionnaire
 336 items. The table shows degrees of freedom (df), F-value and p-value for both factors.

Item	Factor Drive No			Factor ODD		
	df	F	p	df	F	p
Would like to have in car	3, 216	0.2		2, 72	0.4	
Would use if I had it	3, 216	4.9	<.01	2, 72	1.0	
Would use in everyday life	3, 216	3.1	<.05	2, 72	0.2	
I felt safe with the system active	3, 216	1.3		2, 72	5.9	<.01

There was a risky situation with the system active	3, 216	8.4	<.001	2, 72	5.7	<.01
The system was safer than expected	3, 216	5.0	<.01	2, 72	0.9	
I felt safe most time with the system	3, 216	0.6		2, 72	1.7	
I would feel safe without a safety driver	3, 216	8.4	<.001	2, 72	4.8	<.05
I would use the system without a safety driver	3, 216	1.7		2, 72	3.7	<.05
I trust the system	3, 216	1.0		2, 72	5.6	<.01
System behaved appropriately in all situations	3, 216	3.2	<.05	2, 72	5.8	<.01
Using the system was pleasurable most of the time	3, 216	1.3		2, 72	2.6	
Driving with system was pleasurable	3, 216	2.3		2, 72	1.2	
System use was fun	3, 216	5.5	<.001	2, 72	0.1	
With the system I was stressed most of the time	3, 216	4.4	<.01	2, 72	2.8	
Driving with system was demanding	3, 216	2.2		2, 72	1.0	
Would make me tired on long trips	3, 216	4.0	<.01	2, 72	1.4	
With the system I focused more on my environment	3, 216	0.1		2, 72	0.6	
Would use time for NDRAs	3, 216	10.0	<.001	2, 72	0.3	

337

338 Over all drives, motion sickness occurred only very rarely: once in a second drive in the Urban
339 ODD, once in first drive in the Motorway-LC ODD and once in a second drive in the
340 Motorway+LC ODD. Overall, this was too rare to be analyzed with regard to ODD or BA.
341 Willingness to pay for the AD increased significantly with Drive number (ANOVA χ^2 (N=70,
342 $FG=3$) = 7.9 $p = <.05$) but did not differ between ODDs.

343 In the post-drive questionnaire, drivers stated how frequently they would engage in different
344 NDRAs while using ADS in their vehicle. As can be seen in Figure 2, there was a wide range
345 in the popularity of the different NDRAs, with very popular ones like listening to music or
346 interacting with passengers and others to be done only infrequently or never like driving
347 fatigued or reading. Dedicated misuse like sleeping or driving intoxicated were stated as not
348 being done while driving with the ADS. The popularity of the different NDRAs did not change
349 with repeated usage, however there was a difference between ODDs. In the Urban ODD, drivers
350 stated that they would make less frequent video calls ($F(2,72)=4.5$, $p<.05$) or drive fatigued
351 ($F(2,72)=5.5$, $p<.01$). In the Motorway-LC condition without lane changes drivers would more
352 frequently work ($F(2,72)=3.2$, $p<.05$).

353 Urban Motorw-LC Motorw+LC
 354 *Figure 2: Intention to engage in different NDRAs while driving with L3-ADS.*

355 4.2. Mental model

356 There was a significant increase of the percentage of correct answers to the mental model items
 357 with repeated usage ($F(4,288)=4.6, p<.01$, see Figure 3). Furthermore, the percentage of
 358 challenging situations that were believed to be handled by the L3-ADS decreased with repeated
 359 usage ($F(4,288)=39.2, p<.001$, see Figure 3). There was no impact of ODD and no interaction.
 360 Especially for the part of the questionnaire assessing expectations towards the ADS, the biggest
 361 change was between the pre-questionnaire and questionnaires filled in after actual on-road
 362 experience with the ADS.

363 Urban Motorw-LC Motorw+LC Urban Motorw-LC Motorw+LC
 364 *Figure 3: Effect of Drive number and ODD on indicators of the mental model questionnaire. Left:*
 365 *percentage of correct answers; right: percentage of situation believed to be inside ODD.*

366 4.3. System usage

367 As shown in Table 2, there was a significant difference between ODDs in the number of lane
 368 changes conducted ($F(2,71)=196.7, p<.001$). For the Urban ODD, there were on average less

369 than four lane changes per drive, for the Motorway-LC condition 26 lane changes and for the
 370 Motorway+LC condition nearly 43 lane changes occurred. So, in the Urban ODD there was
 371 obviously less need to change lanes compared to the motorway setting. Furthermore, in the
 372 Urban and Motorway-LC ODD, L3-ADS had to be deactivated for all lane changes as they
 373 were outside ODD. For the Motorway+LC ODD, on average 90% of lane changes were
 374 automated lane changes initiated by the ADS and 10% were manual lane changes where the
 375 driver deliberately deactivated the ADS.

376 As can be seen in Figure 4, there was also a significant impact of ODD on the percentage of
 377 time driving with the ADS active ($F(2,71)=30.8, p<.001$). In the Motorway-LC condition, the
 378 ADS was more frequently deactivated as lane changes were outside the ODD and the L3-ADS
 379 had to be deactivated for a lane change. There was a neither significant impact of Drive number
 380 for the percentage of time driving with AD active nor for the number of lane changes driven
 381 manually or for Motorway+LC in automated mode. The observed differences in the usage of
 382 the ADS were mainly due to differences in the ODD but independent of BA.

383 For the percentage of eyes on road, there was a significant impact of condition ($F(2,69)=6.0,$
 384 $p<.01$, see Figure 4) with less on road glances in the Motorway-LC ODD but no impact of drive
 385 number.

386
 387 *Figure 4: Effect of Drive number and ODD on percentage of time ADS was activated, and percentage*
 388 *of time drivers spent looking on the road (PRC).*

389 The most frequent NDRA was the interaction with the passenger that was in our study the safety
 390 driver with on average 34% of time for the Urban ODD; followed by 51% for the Motorway-
 391 LC and 62% for the Motorway+LC ODD. As the percentage of time spent on interaction with
 392 the passenger was largely impacted by the talkativeness of the individual safety driver this
 393 indicator was not analysed further. The use of the personal smartphone was the second most
 394 frequent NDRA with on average 12% of time for the Motorway+LC ODD and 20% for the
 395 Motorway-LC ODD. For that indicator there was no impact of ODD but a significant impact of
 396 Drive No ($F(3,213)=8.0, p<.001$, see Figure 5) which is based on a reduction of time spent on
 397 smartphone usage with increasing experience. The additionally coded NDRA's "interaction with
 398 infotainment system" and "other" occurred only rarely with less than 1% of driving time.

399 A more detailed look into gaze behaviour while attending to NDRA's showed a lower proportion
 400 of eyes on road time while interacting with the smartphone ($F(1,530)=213.3, p<.001$).
 401 Furthermore, there was a significant interaction between the factor smartphone interaction and
 402 Drive Number ($F(3,530)=3.5, p<.05$). The percentage of eyes on road time decreased with
 403 repeated usage while drives interacted with their phone; it stayed on the same level if they were
 404 not attending to the NDRA.

405 \oplus Smartphone inter. \square No smartphone inter. \oplus Urban \square Motorw-LC \oplus Motorw+LC
 406 *Figure 5: Effect of Drive number and ODD on percentage of time that drivers spent on using their*
 407 *smartphone.*

408 4.4. Requests to intervene

409 In some of the drives, extra-long takeover times of more than 15 seconds occurred. Video
 410 coding showed that in most cases this was due to deliberately testing of the behaviour of the
 411 ADS in case of not-reacting to the RTI in a safe situation while the participant was still attentive.
 412 In case this was obvious from the video, the situations were removed from the analysis as they
 413 do neither reflect normal timely takeover reactions nor a safety critical situation. From the
 414 remaining 582 takeover responses, 96% have a TOC rating of 3 or lower indicating that the
 415 situation was solved without errors and was completely safe. For the remaining 22 situations,
 416 all except one were in the range of takeovers with error but no endangerment. The most frequent
 417 errors were inadequate speeds ($N=6$ situations) and too close longitudinal distances ($N=6$
 418 situations). A closer look at the TORs rated as being with errors showed a mixed pictures of the
 419 circumstances leading to that evaluation. Based on the video, the following more detailed
 420 causes were identified: In $N=4$ situations, the driver was on the phone at the moment of the
 421 TOR resulting in delayed but still uncritical reactions; in $N=2$ situations the ADS behaved
 422 inappropriately probably due to reflecting light on the surface, in $N=4$ situations the driver had
 423 issues with the proper takeover reaction because of choosing the wrong button or putting only
 424 one instead of two hands at the steering wheel, in $N=2$ situations the criticality was mainly
 425 caused by the behaviour of another vehicle (tailgating & close cut in).

426 There was a significant improvement of takeover performance (decrease of TOC-rating) with
 427 increasing experience ($F(3, 570)=4.7, p<.01$) from an average TOC-rating of 1.3 to 1.0.

428 Furthermore, takeover performance was better in the Urban and Motorway-LC condition
429 compared to Motorway+LC ($F(2, 570)=13.4, p<.001$, TOC-rating of 1.1 vs. 1.6).
430 On average, it took about 3.2 seconds until drivers put one hand to the steering wheel after a
431 TOR and on average 4.2 seconds until the ADS was deactivated. There was no change of
432 takeover times with repeated usage.

433 4.5. Relation between different indicators

434 As can be seen in Table 5 there were significant correlations between the different attitudinal
435 concepts during the 1st as well as during the 4th drive. Drivers, who experienced high reliability
436 (“System behaved appropriately”) also expressed higher willingness to use, higher experienced
437 safety as well as higher trust and they described the ADS as more useful. Related to all those
438 concepts was a higher intention to attend to NDRAs in case the ADS was evaluated positively.
439 Indicators derived from vehicle data correlated less with other indicators. In both drives, there
440 was a significant correlation between interaction with the smartphone and eyes on road time.
441 The more drivers attended to their phone, the less they looked onto the road. During the first
442 drive, there were no significant correlations between percentage of system activation and other
443 indicators. After the fourth drive, drivers who activated the ADS more reported also higher trust
444 and a higher intention to attend to NDRAs. For the interaction with NDRAs, there was a positive
445 correlation between intention to attend to NDRAs only during the 1st but no longer during the
446 4th drive.
447

448
449

Table 5: Correlations between the indicators applied for the different types of changes for data collected during the 1st and during the 4th session. Red indicates significant correlations.

Type of change	Indicator	Attitudinal							Cognitive		Driver state		Perf.
		Would use it	Useful	Satisf.	I felt safe	Risky sit.	I trust syst.	Sys. beh. appr.	Would do NDRAs	%Smart phone use	was dem.	was stressed	%(Act.)
Drive 1	Perceptive %EyesOnRoad	0.01	-0.09	-0.17	0.00	-0.14	-0.01	0.09	-0.23	-0.40	-0.09	-0.01	-0.09
	Would use it	-	-0.31	0.04	0.31	-0.20	0.39	0.33	0.47	0.13	-0.49	-0.57	0.14
	Usefulness		-	0.12	-0.45	0.29	-0.41	-0.41	-0.30	-0.09	0.35	0.41	-0.14
	Satisfying			-	-0.10	0.00	0.06	0.03	0.01	-0.03	0.34	0.14	-0.09
	I felt safe				-	-0.55	0.71	0.57	0.31	0.19	-0.58	-0.39	0.20
	Risky situation					-	-0.32	-0.56	-0.14	0.19	0.25	0.21	-0.11
	I trust the system						-	0.40	0.30	0.19	-0.40	-0.36	0.16
	Attitudinal System behaved appr.							-	0.23	-0.01	-0.29	-0.18	0.09
	Would do NDRAs								-	0.37	-0.33	-0.42	0.14
	Cognitive %Smartphone Usage									-	-0.20	-0.17	0.09
Driver state was demanding										-	0.54	-0.11	
Driver state was stressed											-	-0.10	
Drive 4	Perceptive %EyesOnRoad	-0.19	0.13	-0.04	-0.06	0.07	-0.02	-0.05	-0.22	-0.55	0.10	0.05	-0.19
	Would use it	-	-0.44	0.23	0.44	-0.19	0.51	0.35	0.47	0.11	-0.44	-0.53	0.09
	Useful		-	0.11	-0.58	0.38	-0.59	-0.47	-0.48	-0.13	0.38	0.41	-0.07
	Satisf.			-	-0.09	0.26	0.07	-0.02	-0.03	-0.09	0.18	0.13	0.10
	I felt safe				-	-0.61	0.85	0.66	0.45	0.14	-0.66	-0.55	0.32
	risky situation					-	-0.51	-0.73	-0.28	-0.09	0.59	0.44	-0.11
	I trust the system						-	0.63	0.37	0.01	-0.50	-0.57	0.21
	Attitudinal System behaved appr.							-	0.27	0.06	-0.49	-0.40	0.14
	Would do NDRAs								-	0.17	-0.34	-0.28	0.29
	Cognitive %Smartphone Usage									-	-0.11	-0.10	0.10
Driver state was demanding										-	0.66	-0.13	

was stressed | | | | 0.04

Preprint not peer reviewed

451 5. Summary and Discussion

452 5.1. Observed behavioural adaptation

453 The aim of the presented study was to investigate BA to L3-ADS in a real-road setting. Building
454 on a simulator study (Metz et al., 2021) which identified behavioural changes on five levels,
455 namely perception, cognition, attitudes, driver state and performance, we conducted similar
456 analyses to assess whether behavioural adaptations are also evident in a real-world setting. Our
457 study confirmed BA for all five investigated areas (see Table 6), indicating that drivers
458 increasingly understand the ADS and use it more effectively over time. As a result, they get
459 more relaxed while driving with the ADS and evaluate the ADS more positively. In detail,
460 drivers believe that they know better when it is necessary to pay attention with increasing
461 experience with the ADS. This is reflected in reduced attention to the driving task while
462 interacting with the personal smartphone. Drivers are also less stressed using the ADS with
463 repeated experience. Our findings are in line with the qualitative model of behavioral adaptation
464 which posits that during the interaction with an automated/assisted driving system changes the
465 user's mental model changes along with attitudes such as trust in the system (Rudin-Brown &
466 Parker, 2004).

467 As can be seen in Table 6, BA occurs for several of the assessed components of acceptance.
468 With increasing experience, the ADS is experienced as more safe and more reliable. In
469 accordance to this, willingness to use and willingness to pay for the ADS increase as well.
470 However, the significant decrease of experienced fun probably indicates an effect of the first
471 encounter phase (Martens & Jenssen, 2012) which goes over into the learning phase after the
472 first contact. Similarly, the expectations towards the capabilities of an L3-ADS decrease
473 significantly during the first encounter. This indicates an adaptation of the cognitive concept of
474 the ADS towards a more realistic mental model of the system's capabilities. Over all four
475 drives, the mental model of the ADS becomes more accurate, which can be interpreted as a
476 direct measure of the learning phase.

477 Another indicator of cognitive changes is the willingness to engage in NDRAs. On a subjective
478 level, the increase in acceptance is reflected in an increase of willingness to attend to NDRAs
479 (similar to results from Metz et al., 2021). However, in contrast to the simulator study, this
480 change in intention is not reflected in actual behavior. In the on-road study, we even observed
481 a decrease of engagement in NDRAs over time. Correlations show that this dissociation
482 between objective and subjective measures of NDRA engagement gets even more pronounced
483 over time.

484 For objective indicators of system handling, no BA is observable or even changes occur that
485 contradicted the subjective results. On the other hand, there are rather strong effects of ODD on
486 those parameters. Therefore, the exact design of the ADS, when and where it can be used and
487 how it needs to be handled for instance in relation to situational affordances strongly impacts
488 indicators of system handling. It seems likely that system design and uncontrolled situational
489 variation are the main factors determining system activation and deactivation whereas the
490 impact of other factors like drivers' attitudes or BA were too small to be observable.

491 Furthermore, it might take some time until drivers adjust their interaction with the ADS in a
 492 way that relations between system evaluation and handling become observable. For instance,
 493 there is a positive correlation between the experienced safety of the ADS and the intention to
 494 attend to NDRAs and the objectively measures percentage of system activation after the fourth
 495 drive but not after the first drive.

496 Takeover performance at the planned RtIs is overall without errors and increases with repeated
 497 usage. This change of performance can be observed in the complex measure of video-based
 498 TOC-rating but not in simple measures of takeover responses like reaction times. In this context,
 499 it is interesting to see that many drivers started testing ADS behavior at system limits (e.g. not
 500 taking control back and observing warning cascade) after having some experience with the
 501 ADS. This type of testing might be a relevant component in the learning phase that might
 502 frequently occur in a natural unsupervised learning process.

503 For other indicators of objectively observed handling of ADS, changes over time are few and
 504 correlations with other indicators are low. In sum, changes due to repeated experience with the
 505 ADS were more pronounced for subjective measures assessed via questionnaires than for
 506 measures based on observed driver behaviour.

507 Overall, the results support the idea of a first encounter phase taking place during first contact
 508 with a system. In our study, the first encounter started with high expectations and fun in testing
 509 a new technology. After the first drive, fun decreased and expectations towards the system's
 510 capabilities became more realistic. In the following learning phase, a continuous increase in
 511 perceived system reliability, experienced safety and other related measures was evident. Based
 512 on our data, it remains inconclusive whether four drives are enough to cover the complete
 513 learning phase and enter the trust phase. Some indicators show minimal change between the
 514 third and fourth drives, suggesting the onset of the trust phase, for others this cannot be
 515 observed. It should be considered that the duration of the learning phase might vary for different
 516 types of changes.

517 *Table 6: Summary of results for behavioural adaption (BA) separately for type of change.*

	Significant effect of BA	No BA measurable
<i>perceptive changes</i>	With repeated usage drivers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • direct less attention to the road while interacting with their smartphone 	With repeated usage there is no change of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • experienced driving related attention • overall percentage of eyes on road time
<i>attitudinal changes</i>	With repeated usage there is <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an increase of experienced safety • an increase of perceived reliability • an increase of willingness to use • an increase of willingness to pay • a decrease of experienced fun 	With repeated usage there is no change of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • trust • usefulness • satisfaction
<i>cognitive changes</i>	With repeated usage there is <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • better knowledge when to pay attention • better knowledge of split of responsibilities • an increase of willingness to attend to NDRAs • a reduction of time spent on NDRAs • an improvement of the mental model 	With repeated usage there is no change of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • percentage of time the system is activated • number of lane changes in ODD

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a reduction of situations believed to be inside ODD 	
<i>driver state changes</i>	With repeated usage drivers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • feel less stressed • report less that driving with the system makes them tired 	With repeated usage there is no change of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reported workload
<i>performance changes</i>	With repeated usage there is <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an improvement of overall takeover performance 	With repeated usage there is no change of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time until drivers react after an Rtl

518

519 5.2. Comparison with findings from simulator study

520 While many findings on behavioural adaptation to L3-ADS of the presented on-road study
 521 confirm those of a similar study conducted in a driving simulator (Metz et al., 2021), one
 522 striking difference is evident: While trust in the ADS increased with repeated usage in the
 523 driving simulator study, trust did not increase in the on-road study. One of the explanations is
 524 that in the simulator study a driving environment was created in which the simulated ADS
 525 worked stable and without unexpected changes in system behavior for all participants. Due to
 526 the prototype status of the on-road system and the natural and uncontrolled variation in driving
 527 situations, environmental conditions and behavior of surrounding traffic in the on-road study,
 528 participants could experience unexpected system behaviors and engagements of the safety
 529 drivers which could have impaired trust-building. Furthermore, in a simulated environment,
 530 participants are aware that there is no actual risk to their safety and well-being. However, it
 531 needs to be noted that overall trust levels were decently high also in the on-road study.

532 While in the simulator study, visual attention to the road decreased with increasing experience
 533 of the ADS, in the on-road study, a decrease in visual attention to the road was only observable
 534 during smartphone usage. It must be noted, however, that the overall attention to the road was
 535 considerably higher in the on-road study and remained on a high level while in the driving
 536 simulator study, attention to the road was on an initial low level and decreased even further
 537 with increasing experience. A plausible explanation for this observation is that even though we
 538 made efforts to design the simulated road environment with attention to details such as different
 539 sceneries, we could not avoid repetitions in the environment. Watching the road environment
 540 might not be as interesting and appealing as watching a real-road environment which could be
 541 one main explanation for the higher attention to the road in the on-road study. Not much
 542 research is available on the comparison of visual attention in real-world as compared to driving
 543 simulator studies. One study compared gaze patterns in junction scenarios in a high-fidelity
 544 driving simulator and real-world scenarios (Robbins, Allen, & Chapman, 2019): The study
 545 found that for high-engagement tasks, gaze patterns were similar in both environments while
 546 for tasks involving less driver engagement, the study found lower levels of visual engagement
 547 with the scene in the simulated environment. In our studies where the ADS was driving most
 548 of the time, the driver engagement can be characterized as very low. Therefore, the lower visual
 549 attention in the simulator study as compared to the presented on-road study is in line with
 550 findings from Robbins et al. (2019).

551 A particularly interesting difference in behavioural adaption to the ADS between the simulator
552 study and the on-road study was that while in the simulator, engagement in NDRAs increased
553 with repeated usage of the ADS, engagement in NDRAs decreased with repeated usage in the
554 on-road study. The engagement with a smartphone was a popular NDRA in both studies (Wörle
555 & Metz, 2020), only engagement with a passenger (i.e., the safety driver) was more popular in
556 the on-road study, a NDRA that was not available in the simulator study. Even though the safety
557 drivers were instructed to limit their engagement with the participants to a bare minimum, the
558 safety drivers adhered to this instruction to varying degrees.

559 5.3. Limitations

560 Other than in the simulator environment, BA could be shown mainly for subjective parameters
561 but not for objective indicators of system handling. Main reason for this is probably the
562 variation of driving situations and environment occurring in the real-world setting. In
563 comparison, in a highly controlled simulated environment also small changes in driver behavior
564 can be found.

565 Especially the results of NDRA engagement while driving with the ADS were surprising. We
566 were not able to create a study environment in which it was possible to observe driver behavior
567 like it would be driving with an ADS while being alone in the car. Instead, the presence of the
568 safety driver created a social situation with frequent interactions. This makes it very difficult to
569 interpret the results of NDRA engagement as the interaction between the two persons in the car
570 as well as the willingness to engage in other NDRAs while being in the presence of someone
571 else, are for sure impacted by the personality of the individual safety driver but probably also
572 by sympathy and increasing familiarity between driver and safety driver. So, it is very
573 challenging to draw conclusion from behavior assessed in a social context to behavior that
574 would occur while being alone in a car.

575 For future studies we recommend to go beyond the four hours of system usage taking place on
576 four days like it was done in this study. To be able to assess the transition into the trust phase
577 more drives seem to be necessary. As soon as L3-ADS has reached a level of maturity to have
578 it tested by ordinary drives in real traffic without a safety driver in the car, it would be much
579 easier to organize studies in which BA can be studied over a longer period of time.

580 5.4. Conclusions

581 Similar to the previously conducted driving simulator study, behavioral adaptations to L3-ADS
582 were evident in the presented on-road study. As drivers' mental models of the ADS improved
583 towards a more accurate understanding, their attitudes towards the ADS became more positive,
584 particularly in terms of willingness to use and pay, confirming the assumptions of the qualitative
585 model of behavioral adaptation (Rudin-Brown & Parker, 2004). However, these positive
586 attitudes did not translate into higher trust levels, possibly because the initial high expectations
587 for the ADS were not met. Unlike the previous simulator study, where an increase in trust was
588 accompanied by lower visual attention to the road, this was not observed in the on-road study.
589 The variations in behavioral adaptation across different ODDs suggest that these adaptations
590 strongly depend on the specific system implementations, which limits the generalizability of

591 the findings. Designing a study to capture "unexpected" real-world behaviors presents
592 considerable challenges, such as limitations introduced by the safety protocols required for
593 testing prototype systems. The presence of a safety driver likely impacts driver behavior
594 especially with regards to potential NDRA's but maybe also with regard to deliberate testing of
595 system boundaries, and the predefined routes limit the participants' scope of action. Despite
596 these challenges, the study provides valuable insights into the interconnections of behavioral
597 adaptations to L3 ADS and emphasizes the importance of considering changes in user behavior
598 through system usage early in the design process.
599

600 **Acknowledgements:** The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's
601 Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101006664. Responsibility for the
602 information and views set out in this publication lies entirely with the authors. The authors would like to thank all
603 partners within Hi-Drive for their cooperation and valuable contribution.

604 **Funding:** The study is part of the research project Hi-Drive (<https://www.hi-drive.eu/>), which receives funding
605 from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101006664.

606 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.
607

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